

Euphorbia proadoa, a Replacement Name for *Euphorbia rhytisperma* (Euphorbiaceae)

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Abstract—The name *Euphorbia rhytisperma* (Klotzsch & Garcke) Boiss is grammatically incorrect and must be corrected to *Euphorbia rhytidosperma*. This renders it an illegitimate younger homonym of *Euphorbia rhytidosperma* Boiss. & Balansa. The replacement name *Euphorbia proadoa* is proposed.

Euphorbia rhytisperma (Klotzsch & Garcke) Boiss. is a species of spurge in *Euphorbia* subsect. *Hypericifoliae* Boiss (Yang et al. 2012) native to South America. The combination was published in 1862, three years after the publication of the name *Euphorbia rhytidosperma* Boiss. & Balansa for a different species.

The authors of the basionym *Anisophyllum rhytispermum* Klotzsch & Garcke supplied no etymology for the specific epithet, but their description of the seeds as ‘having little wrinkles’ (*rugulosis*) indicates a compound of Greek ῥυτίς [*rhytis*] (‘wrinkle’) and σπέρμα [*sperma*] (‘seed’).

As such, the epithet is contrary to Article 60.10 of the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Turland et al., 2018), under which ‘[a]djectival epithets that combine elements derived from two or more Greek or Latin words’ are to be compounded by 1. removing the case ending of the genitive singular of the first word and 2., before a consonant, inserting a connecting *i* (for Latin words) or *o* (for Greek words) between the two words.

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The epithet *rhytisperma* contravenes both provisions of this article: 1. the stem of *rhytis* (genitive singular ῥυτίδος [*rhytidos*]) is *rhytid* rather than *rhyt*; 2. this word being Greek, the connecting vowel should be *o* rather than *i*. The epithet must therefore be corrected to *rhytidosperma*.

This correction renders *Euphorbia rhytidosperma* (Klotzsch & Garcke) Boiss. an illegitimate younger homonym of *Euphorbia rhytidosperma* Boiss. & Balansa. (Even if left uncorrected the name *Euphorbia rhytisperma* is still confusingly similar to *Euphorbia rhytidosperma* and should be treated as a younger homonym under Article 53.3.)

A replacement name is proposed here:

Euphorbia proadoa* M.van der Meer **nom. nov.*

- ≡ *Euphorbia rhytidosperma* (Klotzsch & Garcke) Boiss. ('*rhytisperma*')
—de Candolle, Prodr. 15(2): 43 (1862)
nom. illeg. (ICN Art. 60.10 aut 53.3)
- ≠ *Euphorbia rhytidosperma* Boiss. & Balansa
—Diagn. Pl. Orient. ser. 2, 4: 84 (1859)
- ≠ *Tithymalus rhytidospermus* (Boiss. & Balansa) Soják
—Čas. Nár. Mus., Odd. Přír. 140(3-4): 176 (1972)
- ≡ *Euphorbia rhytidosperma* Engelm. ex Klotzsch & Garcke ('*rhytisperma*')
—Abh. Königl. Akad. Wiss. Berlin 1859: 34 (1860)
nom. inval. (ICN Art. 36.1), pro syn. sub *Anisophyllo rhytidospermo* Klotzsch & Garcke ('*rhytispermum*')
- ≡ *Anisophyllum rhytidospermum* Klotzsch & Garcke ('*rhytispermum*')
—Abh. Königl. Akad. Wiss. Berlin 1859: 34 (1860)
- ≡ *Chamaesyce rhytidosperma* (Klotzsch & Garcke) Soják ('*rhytisperma*')
—Čas. Nár. Mus., Odd. Přír. 140(3-4): 170 (1972)

Etymology: From the Greek *proadoa*, ‘previously lacking “do”’.

Literature

Turland, N. J., Wiersema, J. H., Barrie, F. R., Greuter, W., Hawksworth, D. L., Herendeen, P. S., ... Smith, G. (2018). *International Code of Nomenclature for Algae, Fungi, and Plants (Shenzhen Code): Adopted by the Nineteenth International Botanical Congress, Shenzhen, China, July, 2017*.
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